

Grapheme List of Abnormal Hieratic
pLouvre E 7851, pLouvre E 7852, and pLouvre E 7856
compiled and drawn by
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The following list contains all signs and sign groups of the abnormal hieratic documents pLouvre E 7851 rt + vs, pLouvre E 7852 rt, and pLouvre E 7856 rt + vs. It was compiled in the context of the project The Abnormal Hieratic Global Portal at Leiden University, led by Ferdinand Harmsen, with Koen Donker van Heel as head cooperation partner providing the Egyptological material.

The facsimiles were drawn based on the high-resolution images provided by the Musée du Louvre and published on the website of the Abnormal Hieratic Global Portal (<https://lab.library.universiteitleiden.nl/abnormalhieratic/>). The software LabelMe was used to annotate a facsimile image of the entire document and extract the individual graphemes automatically. The size of some graphemes was slightly adjusted to fit the table format. High-resolution images, hieroglyphic transliteration, transcription, translation, and bibliographical references for the papyri are available on the website of the Abnormal Hieratic Global Portal.

The following people contributed to the creation of the grapheme list: Juan José Archidona Ramírez (helping with deciding on how to classify individual signs and sign groups); Stephan Unter (developing the annotation system with the help of LabelMe and extracting the signs); Cheyenne Cozijnsen (helping with annotation of pLouvre E 7852).

The Abnormal Hieratic Global Portal was intended to be a pilot study, which we had hoped to extend in the future. At the time of writing, this does not appear likely to happen due to the (well-earned) retirement of Koen Donker van Heel in January 2026, hence the decision to publish this small sample, in the hope that it may still be useful to scholars and students of Abnormal Hieratic.

Hamburg, 15.02.2026

Dedicated to Juan José Archidona Ramírez (1992-2024),
dearly missed colleague and friend.

Hieroglyphic sign / sign group Manuel de Codage	pLouvre E 7851	pLouvre E 7852	pLouvre E 7856
rt			
vs			
vs			
rt			
vs			
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rt vs vs			
rt vs vs vs			
vs			

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<p>rt rt</p>			
<p>rt vs vs vs</p>			
<p>rt</p>			
<p>rt</p>			
<p>rt vs</p>			
<p>rt</p>			
<p>rt</p>			
<p>rt rt</p>			
<p>rt rt rt vs vs vs vs vs vs vs vs vs</p>			

<p>II N23</p>			
<p>△ N29:N35</p>			
<p>N35</p>			
<p>N35a</p>			
<p>N35:B1</p>			
<p>N35:D36</p>			
<p>N35:G1</p>			
<p>N35-M17-G17- Y1:I9</p>			
<p>N35:N35:Z2</p>			

<p>rt</p>			
<p>vs</p>			
<p>vs</p>			

 rt			
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Seasons			
Months			

Days			